

IOTier: A Virtual Testbed to evaluate systems for IoT environments

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Abstract—Internet of Things (IoT) is an emerging field characterized by constrained resources, Internet-based communication, arbitrary topologies, geographical distance, and variable operational conditions. Additionally, IoT architectures typically exhibit at least three tiers: IoT devices, Edge gateways, Cloud servers. On top of challenging the design of networked systems, multiple tiers create a web of complexity that makes systems evaluation a challenging endeavor. This paper presents a framework for transforming a cluster of lab machines into a Virtual Testbed that provides views of how systems will perform in a tiered IoT environment. Experiments with constrained resources (CPU, memory, block device, network), multiple tiers, and programmable events are presented and discussed. Their effects are analyzed on the common path operation of micro-benchmarks and distributed key/value store.

Index Terms—IoT, Testbed, Emulator, Systems evaluation,

I. INTRODUCTION

New generations of Internet of Things (IoT) gateways open up huge opportunities for pushing storage and processing tasks from distant Cloud servers, closer to the Things [1]. By shortening the transmission path, IoT gateways are ideal for hosting distributed services of emerging IoT applications such as autonomous vehicles/drones, smart city infrastructure, and augmented reality (AR). However, the capabilities of IoT gateways remain limited compared to the Cloud servers. As such, competitive solutions can only be realized by harnessing the collective power of both Cloud and Edge resources.

Towards finding intelligent ways of placing IoT services across tiers, engineers are facing questions like (i) at which rate the processing power, network bandwidth, geographical distance, and storage capacity affect data services performance? (ii) is it better to keep replicas on the Edge or in the Cloud? (iii) or, under which conditions data placement based upon size is better than data placement upon data temperature (hot/cold)?. To answer the above, engineers need to perform experiments with dozens of moving parts, from low-level device characteristics to high-level placement strategies, and evaluate their impact on latency (timeliness), throughput, congestion, and operational costs.

One solution is to run experiments on real IoT testbeds, such as IoT-LAB [2] or SmartSantander [3]. In this approach, the application is executed on real devices, and the result of its execution is then examined. Although desirable, experimenta-

tion in real testbeds is usually costly and provides few means of understanding how the application works. Moreover, the variable environmental noise and device wearing forfeit the reproducibility of results. Simulation is an alternative solution that is both cheaper and guarantees reproducibility. A simulator represents a system with mathematical models. It further provides programmable events through which operators can evaluate their systems under dynamically changing conditions. On the downside, simulators are usually inappropriate for testing real applications. Emulation is a technique for running real applications over virtual components designed to mimic real devices (e.g., throughput, operations per second). Unfortunately, most emulators today lack support for programmable events, suffer from limited scalability, and do not support tiered architectures.

In this paper, we introduce *IOTier*, an IoT testbed that combines and extends the most important features of existing emulation and simulation techniques. Besides the configurable software stacks for device emulation (e.g., CPU, Memory, IOPS) and network emulation (e.g., bandwidth, delay), *IOTier* provides novel mechanisms for grouping emulated components into tiers. Each tier consists of devices with comparable capabilities and unique networks for inter-tier and intra-tier communications. Moreover, *Timon* provides programmable events used to create self-modifying testbeds that pseudo-randomly alter their operating conditions while running [4]. The interplay of these building blocks allows engineers to recreate tiered IoT environments with dynamically changing operating conditions (e.g., joining/leaving nodes, network outages, or hardware malfunctions). Equally important is that the whole process takes place in near real-time, making it possible to enable interaction with real devices and external IoT services.

The scientific contribution of the paper is as follows:

- (i) a framework tool transform a cluster of lab machines into a software-defined experimentation platform;
- (ii) a collection of real-world performance profiles for various IoT devices and network protocols;
- (iii) validation of emulation techniques and evaluation of a key/value database in a tiered IoT environment.

The remaining of the paper is organized as follows. Sec-

tion II explains the framework’s design and covers its implementation details. Section III and Section IV describe the evaluation methodology and results, in respective order. Sections V refers to the related work, and we conclude the paper in Section VI.

II. IOTIER DESIGN

A. Overview

As shown in Figure 1, we separate the testbed runtime from the testbed controller. The runtime consists of containers in which operators can run images for databases, queuing systems, benchmarks, or any other executable program that runs in a distributed IoT environment. The testbed controller, called *Timon*, provides a YAML file in which operators can express the desired state of the runtime as a function of time. The controller takes that file and performs the necessary actions to maintain the distributed runtime in sync with the desired state.

The idea behind device emulation is to restrict the container’s access to the host’s CPU, Memory, and Storage resources so that the observed performance matches the performance of an actual IoT device. Although throttled resources can mimic the desired performance characteristics, it takes more advanced techniques for mimicking the behavioral characteristics of real-world LAN, WAN, and Internet connections. To achieve a realistic network emulation, we intervene into the network stack and manipulate packets before being transmitted by the network interfaces. Because network policies require intervention at both communicating ends (clients and servers), we decouple the policy enforcement for intelligent policy-making. The policy enforcement takes place in agents running within the containers, whereas the testbed controller takes policy decisions. We also support container agents for telemetry and remote management.

Using the YAML file mentioned above, operators can specify events for controlling the rate at which clients will join or leave the testbed, launch new servers if tail latency goes above a given threshold, or schedule failure events that disrupt vital services. We refer to the interval between consecutive events as a phase. We assume that during a phase, the runtime state remains stable. Besides a declarative way for expressing the desired state, *Timon* also supports various *Microflows* that specify how to reach that state.

A *Microflow* is a series of actions that control how containers will transit from one phase to another. We currently support two *Microflows*: Disjoint and Evolutionary. In *Disjoint*, each phase is autonomous, with the containers starting together, perform a task, and then terminate before the next phase begins. As an example, a *Disjoint Microflow* can be used for automating the execution of numerous short-living distributed tests. In *Evolutionary* each phase is an incremental change to the state of a single long-running test. For example, an *Evolutionary Microflow* can mimic the operating conditions of a dynamic IoT environment, with IoT conditions represented as a sequence of events fired at specific points in time.

B. Device Emulation

A container is a lightweight and isolated process that runs on a host and shares its resources through OS-level virtualization. By default, there are no constraints, and containers can use as much of a given resource as the host’s kernel scheduler allows. If no scheduling priorities are specified, the available host resources are split evenly between running containers. Cgroups are a Linux kernel feature for assigning hardware and system resources to processes. There are two types of resource assignments: ‘limits’ and ‘reservations’. In the context of *IOTier*, we use ‘limits’ to maximize the number of collocated IoT clients per host. Conversely, we use ‘reservations’ to guarantee minimum requirements and minimize the interference between antagonizing containers on the same host. Next, we explain our approach to resource throttling and the respective validation methods.

Memory: For memory, which can be preallocated when a process starts, the mapping between a real device and a constrained container is straightforward. For example, 4GB RAM will be mapped to a 4GB constrained container. To validate memory throttling, we developed a micro-benchmark that allocates chunks of 4MB until an out-of-memory (OOM) error occurs. Our metric is the size of the allocated memory until the error is thrown.

Block I/O: For I/O throttling on block devices, we use the cgroup ‘blkio’ subsystem to specify policies for reads versus writes, and synchronous versus asynchronous I/O. By changing the blkio of each container (/sys/fs/cgroup/blkio) we can configure counters for “write_bps_device”, “read_bps_device”, “write_iops_device”, “read_iops_device”. BPS is defined in bytes per second and limits the block I/O bandwidth. In contrast, IOPS is defined in IO per second and imposes additional delays on I/O requests for containers that exceed the defined limits. For I/O validation, we use fio [5] benchmark to report sequential reads, sequential writes, random reads, and random writes.

CPU: CPU throttling effectively controls how often a process can interrupt the processor or a set of cores of the host. Within each given period, a container can consume up to a ‘quota’ microsecond of CPU time. If the container exceeds its quota (for that period), the cgroup strikes in and disallows the container to run again until the next period. To translate a given CPU profile to the respective CPU Quota, we use the heuristic formula of Equation 1. $Cores$ and $freq_{prof}$ are the cores and the frequency in the CPU profile, whereas $freq_{host}$ is the frequency of the available CPU in the host. To prevent collocated containers from experiencing degraded performance, quota acts simultaneously as ‘limitation’ and ‘reservation’ policies.

We validate the CPU throttling in two different ways: cross-reference and micro-benchmark. Firstly, we reckon that Fogify authors [6] used a similar formulation and evaluated it against Raspberry Pi 3 devices. The results between running the benchmark in real devices are throttled containers are comparable, with only marginal deviations. Second, we obtained

Fig. 1: Illustration of *IOTier* design. The runtime consists of containers running over throttled resources. Containers may connect to multiple virtual overlay networks. The controller provides a centralized way for managing the distributed runtime, and keeps the state of the testbed in sync with the desired state.

the specifications of various CPU architectures evaluated with 7-Zip benchmark [7], translated those specifications into CPU Quotas, and re-run the experiments. The results show a variance of 4%, which solidifies our approach. Additionally, given that 7-Zip is a multi-threaded LZMA compression benchmark, we are sure that multi-threaded services can access all the host’s CPU cores, though quota policies regulate their usage.

$$quota = \sum_{n=1}^{Cores} \frac{freq_{virt}}{freq_{host}} \quad (1)$$

C. Network Emulation

TC [8] is a standard Linux tool that we use to manipulate packets coming in or going out of a specific network interface. When an application sends a packet to the network interface, the Linux kernel first places the packet into a queue managed by TC. The behavior of this queue is configurable via a mechanism called ‘Queueing Discipline’ or ‘qdisc’. Network Emulator (NetEM) is a special qdisc that can delay, drop, or duplicate a packet, as required to match the desired network characteristics, i.e., latency, packet loss, and bandwidth. Netem is a ‘classful qdisc’. Classes form a hierarchical tree, with every class having a single parent and multiple children. The root is the network interface, the intermediate nodes are rules for packet filtering, and the leaves are queues with the desired QoS policies. Qdisc compares the packet against the filtering rules for every incoming or outgoing packet and forwards it to the appropriate queue. New policies can be created dynamically, which allows us to create per network policies and update those policies at runtime.

Policy-making: When a container connects to a virtual network, the container Orchestrator creates a pair of virtual network interfaces. By attaching one side of the pair to the container and the other side to a bridge running on the host (e.g., vSwitch), we enable communication between all containers and the physical network. Upon creation, the

Orchestrator broadcasts a notification that is subsequently captured by *Timon*’s listening service. In turn, *Timon* queries the Orchestrator for information regarding the container and the networks it is connected to. From the response, *Timon* parses metadata (labels) prefixed by “com.timon.*” and creates tuples $\langle Subnet, TC_Rules \rangle$. The Subnet is a unique network subnet representing a tier, and TC_Rules are the traffic rules for the interface connected to that network.

Unfortunately, the network interfaces belong to the container’s namespace and are inaccessible by the container’s Orchestrator. To obtain the interface from which the container accesses a given network, *Timon* queries the container directly using the network’s subnet as the key. Eventually, *Timon* creates the respective TC command (e.g., “tc qdisc add \$INTERFACE \$TC_RULES”), which then forwards it for execution by the TC agent running within the container.

Bidirection Policies: Imagine a scenario where ten clients exchange messages with one server over a link with 150 MB/s bandwidth. A naive approach would be to limit clients to 150 MB/s each. This, however, would lead to over-subscription with the server traffic amounting to 1500 MB/s. Conversely, a static bandwidth allocation would lead to under-subscription since no client will be able to use it all, even if no other clients exist.

A more accurate representation would be to shape incoming traffic on the server. This, however, requires additional instrumentation since qdiscs work by dequeuing packets from a finite buffer, and therefore can only affect the outbound traffic. As there is no way to control the rate at which the buffers fill, it is impossible to throttle incoming traffic directly. For this reason, it is tough to mitigate distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks. A way to address this limitation is through Linux’s Intermediate Functional Block (IFB) device. IFB is a kernel module that creates a pseudo network interface (e.g., ifb0) that acts as a proxy to the physical interface (e.g.,

eth0). Thereby, we can implicitly control the inbound traffic to eth0 by controlling the outbound traffic of ifb0.

Bandwidth Sharing: Enforcing policies on the network interface means that the lowest network stack will start dropping packets after a threshold is exceeded. However, network policies say nothing about bandwidth sharing; a single client can dominate the bandwidth and leave other clients to starve. One way to ensure "fair" bandwidth access is to assume protocols with built-in congestion control, like TCP. Congestion control is a mechanism for detecting contending flows and regulate the transmission rate accordingly. For protocols without congestion control, we mimic intermittent transmissions using a back-off mechanism based on Gaussian jitter. The term jitter refers to random (variable) latency introduced to the packet before being transmitted. This functionality must be enabled manually since *IOTier* is designed to be application-agnostic. Therefore it cannot conclude the proper method without hints from the user.

Composite links: IoT devices rarely interact directly with Cloud servers. In most cases, they send traffic to a nearby IoT gateway via a wireless link, which then forwards traffic to the Cloud via a landline. Thus, we need a way to emulating inter-tier communication. One solution would be to integrate routing software to the containers mimicking the gateways. Besides complicating the deployment, this enforced decision would reduce the flexibility of our testbed, given that routing may happen at several OSI layers (e.g., link, network, transport, application).

Instead, we propose composite links whose network characteristics represent all the intermediate links along the emulated path. In practice, the composite link is a virtual network whose policies are automatically calculated by *Timon* using the formula of Equation 2. For example, a composite link between an IoT and a Cloud server will incorporate the delay from the device to the gateway and from the gateway to the Cloud.

$$\begin{aligned} bandwidth(1...N) &= \min_{link_1, \dots, link_N} \\ delay(1...N) &= \sum_{i=1}^N link_i \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

D. Simulation of operating conditions

Events: Internally, *Timon* runs a simulation engine based on fixed-increment time progression. Whenever an event is fired in the engine, *Timon* executes the respective *Microflow* action to alter the testbed runtime from one state to another. *Timon* supports two kinds of events: Scheduled and Conditional. Scheduled events are self-fired at a particular instant in time. They simulate normal conditions, such as elastic clients and servers, or abnormal conditions, such as crashing nodes, bitrot, intermittent connectivity. Conditional events are fired only if a given expression evaluates to true. Conditional events simulate dependent operations, such as adding a new server if tail latency exceeds a given threshold or create a chain of events, such as cascading failures.

Fig. 2: Microflows overview. The phases, in the respective order, have 1, 8, 16, 1 containers. In Adjoint, containers are killed at the end of each phase. In Evolutionary, containers consistently move from one phase to another.

Microflow: A Microflow is a series of actions that control how containers will transit from one phase to another. Actions are pluggable and are defined by an interface that has the fundamental property that it can be executed by the Microflow manager of *Timon*. Some of the actions taken by the controller upon a fired event include: the interaction with the container Orchestrator the execution of a command within the container (as happens with TC) the synchronization of the distributed containers push logs and metrics into an external system inject failures [9].

To better understand how *Microflows* work, imagine a scenario where phaseA has 1 client, phaseB has 8 clients, phaseC has 16 clients, and phaseD has 1 client. A tick event is scheduled to switch between phases every 3 minutes. Figure 2 illustrates the transitions for two *Disjoint* and *Evolutionary* Microflows. In the *Disjoint* Microflow, containers are killed after the end of the phase. In the *Evolutionary* Microflow, containers have variable lifespans and may shift from one phase to another. For example, the client of phaseA is running throughout the experiment, while clients of phases B and C are transient.

Phase Synchronization: When running experiments with a dynamic number of clients and servers, available machines can reach a point where resources are exhausted and can no longer host additional containers. To prevent this situation, *Timon* preallocates all the containers. For shifting containers from one phase to another, *Timon* provides the following primitives for distributed coordination: (1) group membership (2) barrier synchronization (3) event notification. These respective REST endpoints are: `"/:phase/join/:clientID"`, `"/:phase/ready"`, `"/:phase/done/:clientID"`. The `"/:"` symbol denotes that these parts of the endpoints are used as parameters to the HTTP engine.

Clients join a phase by contacting *Timon* at the `"/:phase/join/:clientID"` and then wait for `"/:phase/ready"` to become True; if not, the client blocks and retries after a timeout. In parallel, *Timon* creates a new entry with the client's identifier in the phase directory; phase barriers and the respective directories are created on the fly. If the total

number of entries equals the group size, meaning all clients have joined the phase, *Timon* changes the returned value of `"/:phase/ready"` to True. If not, it returns False, waiting for more clients to join. Clients acknowledge termination of tasks by calling `"/:phase/done/:clientID"`, and then join the next phase (`/:next_phase/join/:clientID`)

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Profiles of IoT components

Besides having a competitive benchmark, configuring the benchmark with real-world parameters is essential for getting realistic results. Motivated by that, we organized a collection of performance profiles for various devices and network protocols that we regard as representative of emerging IoT ecosystems. Table I shows the performance profiles for high-end user devices and IoT gateways. Figure 3 shows the performance profiles for real-world network protocols. It includes short-range wireless networks (802.11n, 5g), long-range wireless networks (4G LTE, Starlink), and Internet-based landlines (DSL, Cable, Fiber).

Although the manufacturer’s specifications for CPU, memory, and IOPS can accurately represent real-world performance, this is not the case for network protocols. Physical factors like signal attenuation and multipath effects typically cause the performance of network devices to be orders of magnitude less than their nominative values. For greater fidelity, we structured our network profiles using values obtained from benchmarks with real network equipment [10] and user-experience reports from broadband and mobile providers. More specifically, we used Broadband Deployment Data and Mobile Deployment Data reports, published from Federated Communications Commission [11].

B. Experiments

To demonstrate the effectiveness of *IOTier*, we used our prototype to understand how a key-value store will behave when deployed in the IoT environment of Figure 4. Containers representing ‘Things’ are configured according to the performance profile of Microsoft Hololens. In contrast, containers representing Gateways are configured according to the Dell Edge 5100. For containers representing Cloud servers, no constrained are enforced and can consume all the available host resources. Notably, the link between Thing and Cloud is composite. Its network distance is a function of Thing to Edge and Edge to Cloud.

Using this tiered environment, we design experiments to answer the following questions:

- 1) Is there merit in using powerful servers over a slow network?
- 2) How does a database server respond to transient clients and bursty traffic that dominate IoT?
- 3) What is the impact of running a distributed database at both Edge and Cloud nodes?
- 4) Does a fast network provide more stable performance than a slow one?

- 5) Is it better for an Edge to make replicas on other Edge nodes or to the Cloud?

Network baselines: To establish network baselines, we used containers running iperf benchmark [12], in a server/client architecture. Using *Disjoint Microflow*, we run multiple tests, and in each test, we evaluate a different profile of Figure 3, for a different number of clients. Importantly, the CPU, memory, and storage resources of containers remain unthrottled. The only enforced policies are about the network. This deliberate decision aims to saturate the network in order to observe artifacts in bandwidth sharing.

Server Contention: This experiment demonstrates the interplay of device emulation, network emulation, and scheduled events of *Evolutionary Microflow*. The setup is like before, but instead of iperf, the servers are now running the TiKV [13] key/value store. The clients run the YCSB benchmark [14], configured according to TPCx-IoT workload [15] (v1.0.5). We use one long-running client acting as a reference for the measurement of tail latency. Through scheduled events, we make transient clients appear and disappear periodically. The experiment starts with 1 server and 1 client, then new clients are gradually added. Once 32 clients are reached, the newest 31 clients are killed while the older client keeps running. We evaluate this experiment in two different scenarios: (1) Things send traffic Edge nodes (2) Things send traffic Cloud nodes.

Load balancing: We shift our focus from dynamically added clients to dynamically added servers in this scenario. We evaluated two symmetric configurations: 1) start with a Cloud node and then add the Edge nodes 2) start with an Edge node and then add the Cloud nodes

Replication: Whereas the goal in the Load balancing experiment was to stress inter-tier communication, the goal in the replication experiment is to stress intra-tier communication. To do so, we enable server-to-server communication by increasing the number of database replicas from one to three. We evaluate this experiment in four different scenarios: (1) clients send traffic to Cloud nodes (2) clients send traffic to Edge nodes (3) clients send traffic to 1 Cloud node and 3 Edge nodes (4) clients send traffic to 3 Cloud nodes and 1 Edge node.

IoT Devices	Microsoft Hololens	Dell Edge 5100		
Application	Haptics	Gateway		
CPU	3 GHz	1.3 GHz		
Memory	4 GB	8 GB		
Storage (Profile)	UFS 2.1	SSD M.2		
Network (Profile)	802.11ac 2x2, BT	4G, 802.11n, 1Gbit ethernet		
Storage Profile	Seq.Read	Seq.Write	Rand.Read	Rand.Writer
UFS 2.1	880 MB/s	200 MB/s	40K IOPS	40K IOPS
SSD M.2	2 GB/s	700 MB/s	170K IOPS	130K IOPS

TABLE I: Performance profiles for IoT devices. Interoperability between the devices is feasible because 802.11ac is backward compatible with 802.11n

IV. EVALUATION

We run this evaluation on 3 dedicated 16-core machines (2 CPU sockets with Xeon E5-2630v3). Each machine has 256

Fig. 3: Performance profiles for network protocols. The values represent real-world measurements and may deviate significantly from their theoretical maximum. The 80211n profile is for 2x2 MIMO configuration that can establish up to two data streams within the receiving device.

Fig. 4: Model of a tiered IoT environment in *IOTier*. The intra-tier networks (Cloud-To-Cloud and Gateway-To-Gateway) are not accessible outside of their tier, thus making client-to-server network is different from the server-to-server network. The Things-To-Cloud is composite and its network distance is calculated using Equation 2.

GB of DD3 ECC main memory and an NVM-e providing a read bandwidth of 3GB/s and a write bandwidth of 1GB/s, as reported by fio. The machines are connected to a 100GigE top-of-rack switch that provides full bisection bandwidth.

A. Network Link Emulation

Figure 5 shows that the network policies are effective and the bandwidth is fairly divided amongst the clients. There are, however, a few interesting artifacts. Although theoretical profiles of Figure 3 are well distributed, Figure 5a shows that all networks converge on latency of around 200ms. The first reason is that theoretical profiles indicate delay (in each direction), whereas Figure 5a indicates round-trip time (RTT). As a result, the observed values should be at

least twice the indicated delay. The second reason is that the network policies are applied twice. Once the packet leaves the client, and once the server receives the packet. Combining the above factors, the expected RTT is four times the delay of a given network profile. Also, RTT time (and therefore latency) remains stable unless the network is fully saturated and the per-client throughput goes below 10 MB/s.

B. Server Contention

Figure 6 shows the impact of transient clients to a long-running client. This experiment enabled us to discover a bug in the go-ycsb implementation of YCSB; whenever tail-latency goes above 1 second, the reported value is 0. The network can sufficiently accommodate up to 16 clients, after which the tail latency increases exponentially. Another interesting point is that the Things-To-Cloud network degrades earlier than Things-To-Edge. This is perhaps counter-intuitive since an end-to-end path with multiple hops would have more available network resources to absorb the traffic. For example, if a client sends traffic to a distant server via 3 intermediate nodes (Client \rightarrow A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow Server), there are 5 different networks to absorb the traffic. This, however, would require intermediate nodes to run middleware software. Instead, *IOTier* is based on direct composite links; therefore, this property cannot be examined.

Figure 6b shows the database throughput (Queries per second). The results show that Edge devices can yield greater throughput than Cloud devices, which is reasonable given the significantly better connectivity. More importantly, it shows that the performance of long-running clients never recovers fully after transient clients disappear. The caveat is that transient clients have ingested new data in the system. Therefore the average time for a query is slightly increased.

C. Load Balance

There is initially one client and one server in this experiment, with more servers being gradually added. If we start with a Cloud node and then add a new Edge node, the performance remains stable. In contrast, if we begin with an Edge node and add a new distant Cloud node, the performance fluctuates significantly. The results reveal an interesting property. TiKV features Placement Drivers (PD) that periodically monitor the load on TiKV servers and makes data placement and load balancing decisions. The faster the link is, the quicker the server becomes overloaded, causing frequent rebalancing actions. In turn, the more frequent the data placement changes are, the more the system performance destabilizes.

D. Replication

Figure 8 shows the impact of intra-tier communication to replication. Given that the Edge-to-Edge replication is 60% slower than Cloud-To-Cloud replication, we conclude that there is no point in having powerful Edge nodes without first improving the Edge-to-Edge communication. With another reading, this means that Edge-to-Edge communication must be kept to a minimum. Instead, as indicated by line

Fig. 5: Bandwidth sharing for virtual networks. To improve readability, we omit the names of protocols not used in the evaluation model. Notably, the latency starts increasing only after the per-client bandwidth drops below 10MB/s.

Fig. 6: Contention

Fig. 7: Load balance

Fig. 8: Replication

”Mix_3cloud_1edge” shows, the best approach for ingestion-heavy workloads is to ingest data on the Edge nodes and then replicate it asynchronously to the Cloud. The reason is that packets are acknowledged faster, and Things can continue with the other packets without waiting for acknowledgments from distant Clouds.

Additionally, the network congestion is minimal due to spreading the load among three different networks: Things-To-Gateway, Gateway-To-Cloud, Cloud-To-Cloud. At this point, a clarification must be made. In the Contention experiment, we argued that clients could not benefit from the available resources in a multi-hop path because *IOTier* is based on composite links instead of routing nodes. Although this is

true, replication is an intriguing exception. By injecting data from Things are replicating data to the Clouds, Edges nodes essentially become a kind of ‘asynchronous’ routers.

V. RELATED WORK

Simulators like CloudSim [16], and IoT derivatives such as iFogSim [17] and IoTSim-Edge [18], have been proposed as a cost-effective way for modelling Cloud, Edge, and IoT environments. Though reproducible and convenient, simulators study behaviors expressed as mathematical models with certain assumptions. Hence, they are there inadequate for evaluating real systems.

Emulators incur similar infrastructure costs with simulators while achieving better realism since they run real codes. There are mainly two types of emulators: 1) Full-system emulators, such as ModelNet [19] and DieCast [20], which use VMs as hosts to emulate heterogeneous nodes with various OSes. 2) Container-based emulators, such as FogBed [21], EmuFog [22], and EmuEdge [23], which leverage containers that share a single OS kernel to provide better scalability, required to emulate large-scale IoT infrastructures. Nonetheless, since they are immediate descendants from network emulators, computation and storage realism is usually overlooked. Still, they lack scalability merits and support for dynamic alteration of the testbed structure.

The closest work to ours is Fogify [6]. The two tools share many architectural similarities and are designed to study ‘what-if’ scenarios. The most remarkable difference is that *IOTier* is designed with bottom-up support for tiered architecture. An additional difference is that *IOTier* uses an abstraction layer that makes possible the integration with numerous container Orchestrators, including Docker-Compose for local usage and Kubernetes for clustered deployments.

VI. CONCLUSION

We presented *IOTier*, a container-based framework for transforming a cluster of lab machines into a testing platform for IoT applications. *IOTier* approaches device emulation by limiting the container’s access to the host’s resources, and network emulation by manipulating the packets before they are transmitted by a network interface. *IOTier* enables operators to write testing scenarios in the form of events that alter the testbed structure at runtime. The experiments were focused on the interplay of device capabilities, network distances, and placement strategies, allowing us to understand how a key-value store would behave if deployed in an IoT environment. We detected unusual behaviors and identified critical aspects that need improvement. Given that, we foresee that virtual testbeds like *IOTier* will play an essential role in designing and evaluating future IoT systems.

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